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Problems Confronting Operators of Private Primary and Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study examined the problems confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Three specific purposes, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 130 (39 private secondary school and private primary school) operators in the local government area, which was used as the sample for the study. Researchers structured a questionnaire titled "Problems Confronting Operators in Private Schools Questionnaire (PCOPSQ)" for data collection. Data were analysed with an independent t-test tool. The findings revealed that inadequate funds, inadequate infrastructures, and inadequate instructional materials are problems that confront the operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The study concluded that these challenges could impede students' learning experiences, limit educational opportunities, and hinder overall academic achievement; and addressing them is crucial for ensuring equitable access to quality education and fostering positive learning outcomes. Based on the findings, the study recommended, among others, that private school management should make adequate funding a top priority by creating and implementing sustainable funding strategies. They should focus on improving infrastructure and

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also prioritise the provision of instructional materials, such as textbooks, digital resources, and hands-on equipment, to enhance teaching and learning opportunities.

Keywords: problems, school operators, primary school, secondary school

Introduction

The history of private ownership in educational administration in Nigeria could be traced to the period when Western education was introduced to the country, in the 19th century. As at the time in question, missionaries and churches played dominant roles towards the development and administration of education. Even when the colonial and self-governments took over the control, the significance of education towards national development made private individuals, communities and even both the local and international organisations have interest in the development of education at all levels.

Thus, Ade-Ajayi (2023) stated that education is the mechanism by means of which a society generates the knowledge and skills required for its own survival and sustenance and which it transmits to future generations through the process of instruction to its youths. Society can only develop and exist decently and wisely if it ensures that its educational system is adequate, relevant and sustainable. Also, against the background of the apparent inertia of the government apparatus in providing quality education for the teeming population, it becomes expedient that private initiative in education be facilitated and encouraged. Formal education begins with nursery or pre-primary education, which is the education given in day care centres and nursery schools to children aged between 0 and 6 years. It is enriched by the informal traditional upbringing given to the children of ages 0 to 3 years, which prepares them for school. The government is not directly involved in the establishment of daycare centres and nursery schools. The foundation of education of the child is the preschool education, which forms an integral part of his or her early education, which may be formal or informal and which is given in an educational institution to children aged 3 to 5 years plus prior to their entering into the primary school (National Policy on Education, 2004). This educational level of the child provides for the physical, motor, health, nutritional, intellectual,

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aesthetic, emotional and social development of the preschool child. If child education can provide these vital necessities which are fundamental in human life, it is not therefore unlikely to have an important and strong relationship with the pupils' performance at the primary school level and perhaps at the secondary and tertiary levels (Nakpodia, 2023). The Universal Basic Education Act of 2000 cites nursery education (ECE), which has to do with the early education of children between ages one and five, as an integral part of basic education.

It represents the first important step in achieving the goals of education for all (EFA). Since it is the foundation for a lifelong education, government is expected to be actively involved in providing it for the younger children. Evidence on the ground, however, has shown that parents, private individuals and religious bodies constitute the largest proprietorship of ECE, while government agencies provide a paltry 10%. Adenipekun (2019) notes that this abysmally low government participation in proprietorship of daycare centres and nursery schools denies the poor, disadvantaged and marginalised groups' access to ECE (Early Childhood Education). In fact, nursery education, which falls under pre-primary education, provides for the physical, health, nutritional, intellectual, aesthetic, emotional and social development of the preschool child (Nakpodia, 2016). 'Primary' means 'first' and is the first stage of formal education. Primary education studies as a field of study have attracted much attention and concern from the government, educationists and parents because this primary education level is most crucial and fundamental to Nigeria's future educational stability. It serves as the springboard and holds the key to the success or failure of the whole system of our education. Its popularity is evidenced by the launching of universal primary education (UPE) by the federal government in 1976. Though its implementation is not without hitches, it has recorded tremendous success; hence, the federal government has taken various devices and means to protect this level of education. Today, the Federal Ministry of Education has established a National Primary Education Commission (NPEC) with its headquarters in Kaduna. The state ministries of education have their own units of this board. Local government authorities also have their constituted bodies charged with the coordination of primary education matters

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along with the state's and Nigeria's formulated policies. Primary education studies are also becoming popular in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

A good number of Nigerian universities and colleges of education have units or departments that teach or undertake research activities related to primary education. In fact, two or three universities in Nigeria now offer courses leading to a degree in primary education. Our colleges of education are not left out in this race to improve the quality of education at the primary school level by introducing the course in their curriculum. Most of these colleges of education are of the view that every trainee teacher ought to be exposed to the content, methods, evaluations and administration of education in "the foundation years" of our school system. From these explanations, it thus seems apparent that the study of primary education has gained more attraction and interest among researchers in the Nigerian educational scene.

Private primary and secondary schools play an important role in complementing public education, especially in countries like Nigeria. However, operators of these schools face several serious challenges that affect the quality of education they provide. Among the most critical problems are inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, and inadequate instructional materials. One of the major problems confronting private school operators is insufficient funding. Unlike public schools that receive government support, private schools depend largely on tuition fees paid by parents and, in some cases, small private investments. Many parents struggle to pay fees regularly due to economic hardship, which directly affects the financial stability of the school. As a result, school owners often find it difficult to pay teachers' salaries, maintain facilities, or invest in modern educational resources. This can lead to poor staff motivation, high teacher turnover, and reduced overall school performance. In some cases, schools are forced to operate on very tight budgets, limiting their ability to expand or improve standards. Another major challenge is the lack of adequate infrastructure. Many private schools operate in rented apartments or makeshift buildings that were not originally designed for educational purposes. This leads to overcrowded classrooms, poor ventilation, and lack of essential facilities such as libraries, laboratories, playgrounds, and sanitation systems.

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The absence of proper infrastructure negatively affects the teaching and learning environment. Students may find it difficult to concentrate in uncomfortable classrooms, while teachers may struggle to deliver lessons effectively. Additionally, poor infrastructure can pose safety risks, especially in cases where buildings are not structurally sound. Instructional materials are essential for effective teaching and learning. These include textbooks, teaching aids, laboratory equipment, visual aids, and digital learning tools. Many private schools, however, cannot afford to provide adequate and up-to-date instructional materials due to limited financial resources. This shortage limits teachers' ability to use diverse teaching methods and makes lessons less engaging and practical. Students, in turn, may rely heavily on rote learning instead of developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In science subjects, especially, the lack of laboratory equipment makes it difficult for students to gain hands-on experience. Moreover, private schools may not always offer the same level of transparency and accountability as public schools, which are accountable to the government and subject to various regulations and oversight (Obasi, 2020). Private schools may also be selective in their admission process and may not enrol students with disabilities or those from low-income families, which can perpetuate social inequalities. However, outside these disadvantages, private operators of primary and secondary schools have some challenges in operating these schools.

Some of these challenges, as identified by Eze and Okeke (2023), include inadequate funds, infrastructure, instructional materials, shortage of teachers and security. In this study, inadequate funds, infrastructure, and instructional materials were examined. Inadequate funds are one of the biggest challenges for private operators of primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. According to Aina (2016), funds can refer to money or financial resources that are set aside or available for a specific purpose. This can include money that is saved, invested, or allocated for use by an individual, organisation, or government. Funds can also refer to specific financial instruments or products, such as mutual funds, hedge funds, or exchange-traded funds, which pool investors' money to invest in a variety of assets (Gbenga, 2023). However, the high cost of operating private schools in Nigeria, coupled with limited access to funding and other financial challenges, can make it difficult for

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private school operators to sustain their operations over the long term. Private schools typically require significant financial resources to cover expenses such as teacher salaries, facilities maintenance, instructional materials, and administrative costs. Another challenge of operating private schools in Nigeria is inadequate infrastructural facilities.

According to Adeoye and Adegbite (2024), in the context of schools, infrastructural facilities refer to the physical facilities and resources that are required to support teaching and learning activities. These can include classrooms, laboratories, libraries, computer rooms, playgrounds, sports fields, and other amenities. However, some of the infrastructural facilities are expensive, the government does not support some of these facilities, and there is limited access to credit facilities, and many more. As a result, this can affect the quality of education, health, and safety of pupils, students and staff in private primary and secondary schools. More so, lack of instructional materials can affect the operations of private primary and secondary schools. According to Okeke (2019), instructional materials are any resource used by teachers to facilitate the teaching and learning process in the classroom. These materials can include textbooks, workbooks, handouts, visual aids, manipulatives, and multimedia resources. Ibrahim (2018) posited that some instructional materials can be expensive to procure, especially for private schools that may not have the financial capacity to purchase a wide range of materials.

Also, some instructional materials in Nigeria may be of poor quality, outdated, or not relevant to the curriculum, which can affect the quality of education offered by some private schools as well. Nigerians are becoming comfortable with enrolling their children and wards in private primary and secondary schools. This is due to the poor handling of these schools by the Nigerian governments, from which the state governments are not exempted. As a result, these private operators seem to determine the quality of education in the country. Unfortunately, Akwa Ibom State is not exempted in this situation, thereby leaving the educational upbringing at the mercy of private operators. However, with these challenges, the academic performance of pupils and students might be affected. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine challenges confronting the operators of private primary and secondary schools, especially in Akwa Ibom State, with

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school level (primary and secondary schools) as the moderating variable in the study.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of private primary and secondary education continues to face several challenges that hinder effective teaching and learning. One major problem is the employment of unqualified teachers who lack professional training from recognised institutions such as universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education. This situation negatively affects the standard of instruction delivered to learners.

In addition, inadequate financial support from government authorities has contributed to poor infrastructural development and a shortage of essential instructional materials in many schools. Facilities such as textbooks, libraries, desks, chairs, and tables are insufficient, thereby creating an un conducive learning environment. In some schools, pupils are forced to sit on the floor, stand during lessons, or bring chairs from home due to the lack of furniture. Even where chairs are available, many classrooms lack proper desks for writing.

Another major issue is overcrowded classrooms, which limit effective classroom interaction, reduce ventilation, and make teaching and learning difficult. This challenge is further worsened by the increasing enrolment of pupils without corresponding expansion in school facilities.

Furthermore, although the rapid establishment of private primary and secondary schools appears to provide an alternative to public education challenges, the high tuition fees charged by many of these schools make them inaccessible to average and low-income families. Consequently, quality education in such schools remains largely available to children from wealthy homes, thereby widening educational inequality.

Objectives of the study

The study focuses on the problems confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

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Specifically, the study sought:

- i. Examine inadequate funds as a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
- ii. Determine the inadequate infrastructural facilities as a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. Find out the inadequate instructional materials as a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following questions were postulated in line with the specific purpose of the study.

1. To what extent is inadequate funding a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?
2. To what extent are inadequate infrastructural facilities a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?
3. To what extent is inadequate instructional material a problem confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of inadequate funds on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant influence of inadequate infrastructural facilities on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
3. There is no significant influence of inadequate instructional materials on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Definition of terms

Challenge: A call to someone to participate in a competitive situation or fight to decide who is superior in terms of ability or strength.

Private: Belonging to or for the use of one particular person or group of people only.

Primary School: a school for children between the ages of about five and eleven.

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Secondary School: It is often referred to as a high school and is a school which provides secondary education, between the ages of 11 and 19 depending on location, after primary school and before higher education.

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design to investigate the problems confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Survey research design involves the collection of information from a sample of respondents for the purpose of analysing data to obtain meaningful outcomes, as noted by Check and Schutt (2018). The population of the study comprised one hundred and thirty (130) operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, based on the 2025/2026 enrolment report of the National Association of Proprietors of Private Schools (NAPPS). Using the simple random sampling technique, thirty percent (30%) of operators were selected from schools located in both rural and urban areas, resulting in a sample size of thirty-nine (39) operators.

Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled *Problems Confronting Operators in Private Schools Questionnaire (PCOPSQ)*. The instrument was divided into Sections A and B, where Section A elicited respondents' demographic information, while Section B focused on issues relating to the study variables. To ensure validity, the instrument was vetted by the researcher's supervisor and experts in tests and measurements, who made necessary corrections before approving it for use. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to respondents after obtaining permission from school proprietors. The data generated from the study were analysed using the independent t-test statistical tool at the 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis

Hypothesis One: There is no significant influence of inadequate funds on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

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Table 1: t-test analysis of influence of inadequate funds on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State

Variables (x)	N	X	S.D	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
inadequate Fund	20	44.4	20.58	5.13	1.686	Ho ₁ Rejected
operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State	19	31.16	15.17			

Level of Significance at 0.05, Df =37

The analysis of hypothesis 1 reveals that the mean score of inadequate funds is 44.4 with the standard deviation score of 20.58, while the mean scores of operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State are 31.16 and 15.17, respectively. The calculated t-value of 5.13 is greater than the critical value of 1.686 at 37 degrees of freedom, at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated for the study was rejected, thereby accepting the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is significant influence of inadequate funds on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant influence of inadequate infrastructural facilities on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: t-test analysis of influence of inadequate infrastructural facilities on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State

Variables (x)	N	X	S.D	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
inadequate infrastructural facilities	34	40.5	17.70	4.24	1.686	Ho ₂ Rejected
operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State	19	31.16	15.17			

Level of Significance at 0.05, Df =37

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The result of data analysis in table 2 revealed that the mean score of inadequate infrastructural facilities is 40.5 and the standard deviation score is 17.70, while the mean scores of operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State are 31.16 and 15.17, respectively. The calculated t-value of 4.24 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.686 at 37 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the stated null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is upheld. This implies that there is significant influence of inadequate infrastructural facilities on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant influence of inadequate instructional materials on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: A t-test analysis of the influence of inadequate instructional materials on the operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Variables (x)	N	X	S.D	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Inadequate of instructional materials	32	42.4	21.58			
Operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.	19	31.16	15.17	4.13	1.686	Ho3 Rejected

Level of Significance = 0.05, Df = 37

The analysis of hypothesis 3 reveals that the mean score of inadequate instructional materials is 42.4 with the standard deviation score of 21.58, while the mean scores of operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State are 31.16 and 15.17, respectively. The calculated t-value of 4.13 is greater than the critical value of 1.686 at 37 degrees of freedom at the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stated for the study was rejected, thereby accepting the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is significant influence

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of inadequate instructional materials on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

From the above findings, inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities and inadequate instructional materials are problems confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

From the result of data analysis 1, there is significant influence of inadequate funds on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This result is in line with the findings of Bamidele and Odukoya (2023), who found that inadequate funding was a major challenge for private school operators, leading to a lack of resources and facilities, difficulty in paying teachers, and higher tuition fees for parents.

The result of data analysis in table 2 also revealed that there is significant influence of inadequate infrastructural facilities on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This result finds support in the study by Adebowale and Adebowale (2024), who found that inadequate infrastructure was a major challenge for private school operators, leading to overcrowded classrooms, insufficient learning materials, and poor sanitation facilities.

Finally, the study reveals that there is significant influence of inadequate instructional materials on operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. This result finds support in the study by Ibrahim (2018), who posited that some instructional materials can be expensive to procure, especially for private schools that may not have the financial capacity to purchase a wide range of materials. Hence, to this end, to improve the academic performance of students, the application of suitable teaching techniques becomes relevant to deal upon.

Conclusion

This study examined the problems confronting operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Three specific purposes, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 130 (39 private

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secondary school and private primary school) operators in the local government area, which was used as the sample for the study. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, and inadequate instructional materials significantly affect the operators of private primary and secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study concluded that these challenges could impede students' learning experiences, limit educational opportunities, and hinder overall academic achievement; and addressing them is crucial for ensuring equitable access to quality education and fostering positive learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Ministry of Education should increase support and oversight for private schools by providing access to grants or subsidies to mitigate financial constraints.
- ii. Operators of private schools should prioritise efficient financial management and explore partnerships to secure funding and improve infrastructure and instructional materials.
- iii. Teachers should adopt creative teaching methods and maximise available resources to deliver quality education despite material constraints.
- iv. Students should adapt to available learning environments and engage in self-directed learning to supplement the instructional resources provided.
- v. Parents should actively contribute financially or through volunteering to support their children's schools in addressing resource challenges.

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“PROBLEMS CONFRONTING OPERATORS IN PRIVATE SCHOOLS QUESTIONNAIRE (PCOPSQ)

SECTION A

Please supply the require information and tick (√) where necessary against the option that most applicable to you.

Name of Your School: _____

Gender: Male () Female ()

SECTION B

INADEQUATE FUND AND OPERATORS OF PRIVATE PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

S/N	VARIABLE STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Inadequate funding makes provision of teaching materials difficult				
2	Inadequate funding negatively affects the provision of laboratory equipment for schools				
3	Inadequate funding leads to dilapidation of school infrastructure				
4	Inadequate funding hinders professional development for primary school employees				
5	Inadequate funding increases operational costs				

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INADEQUATE INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITIES AND OPERATORS OF PRIVATE PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

S/N	VARIABLE STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
6	Inadequate infrastructural facilities make learning tedious for learners				
7	Dilapidated school infrastructural facilities creates unconducive environment for learners				
8	Poor school infrastructural facilities dampens teachers' morale				
9	Deficits in infrastructural facilities negatively affects classroom climate				
10	Inadequate infrastructural facilities negatively affects delivery of teaching contents				

INADEQUATE INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS AND OPERATORS OF PRIVATE PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE

S/N	VARIABLE STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
11	Inadequate instructional materials hinders learners' interest				
12	Poorly designed instructional materials make learning difficult				
13	Inadequate instructional materials reduce teachers' efficiency				
14	Inadequate instructional materials limits learners' learning opportunities				
15	Inadequate instructional materials reduce learners' motivation to learn				